

ANALYSIS OF ABDULLA ORIPOV'S POEM "MAYMUNIYAT"

Kakisheva Gulnur Annadurdiyevna

Nukus State Pedagogical University named after Ajinyoz Institute
Faculty of Turkic Languages Turkmen language and Student of the 3-D
group, literature direction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15401157>

Abstract: This article presents an analysis of Abdulla Oripov's poem "Maymuniyat". In this poem, the author criticizes some of the ignorance of mankind through the image of a monkey, encouraging the reader to think deeply.

Keywords: poem, monkey, society, vice, poet, work, human, scientist, image, analysis, criticism.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен анализ поэмы Абдуллы Орипова «Маймуният». В этой поэме автор критикует некоторые невежества человечества через образ обезьяны, побуждая читателя к глубоким размышлениям.

Ключевые слова: поэма, обезьяна, общество, порок, поэт, труд, человек, ученый, образ, анализ, критика.

Abdulla Oripov is an Uzbek poet, translator and public figure. A prominent representative of Uzbek literature and poetry of the 20th century and a Hero of Uzbekistan. He has been writing and practicing poetry since his youth. Abdulla Oripov wrote such poetry collections as "Mitti Yulduz", "Ko'zlarim yo'lingda", "Onajon", "Chashma", "Uzbekistan", "Hayrat", "Yurtim Sh'amoli", "Najot Qalasi", "Yillar Armoni", "Ishonch K'prikleri".

The main theme of the poet's poetry is the Motherland, the country, and nationality. Some of his poems are composed of a combination of philosophical depth and lively lyricism, symbolic images, irony, allegory, and wordplay. One of his poems written on such a theme is "Maymuniyat".

The poem "Maymuniyat" by Abdulla Oripov was written in 1986 in finger-weight. This poem is written in a satirical style, revealing some of the vices of society through the images of humanity and a monkey. Irony and satire are prominent in the work. The image of the monkey in the poem considers itself the crown of the universe. In its thoughts, it claims to be a poet, sees itself as a leader of its time and tries to stand above humanity. It overestimates its abilities and is overconfident. Through this image, we can see people in the world of poetry who have a weak pen, but consider themselves to be great poets.

The monkey begins to write poetry, and the animals in the forest do not oppose him. This is a condemnation of the lack of true criticism or analysis in society, and of blind respect and title. It is understood that the poet in the work is satirizing not only poets, but also people from different strata of society who consider themselves too intelligent, but in reality have fallen to the lowest level.

The monkey's connection with humans, relying on Darwin's theory, even suggests that famous literary figures such as Gulkhani and Krylov are descended from monkeys. This shows that the author misinterprets simple scientific truths.

As for the rhyme scheme of the work, it rhymes in the form aaaa and consists of 13 syllables. The monkey is an allegorical (symbolic) image in the poem.

In general, the author criticizes some of the ignorance of mankind through the image of a monkey, encouraging the reader to think deeply.

References:

- 1.S. Mirvaliev, Uzbek writers.
- 2.Qoshjonov M., Suvon M. Abdulla Oripov. Tashkent: "Ma'naviyat", 2000.
- 3.[https //en.wikipedia.org/](https://en.wikipedia.org/)

